

TERMIZ STATE UNIVERSITY, LINGUISTICS: UZBEK LANGUAGE
MASTER'S STUDENT

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Semantic features of modern ergonyms in Uzbek

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ANNOTATION

Ergonyms are the names of organizations and institutions, which are deeply studied in various fields of onomastics, and their collection enriches historical sources. The article talks about the principles and types of ergonomics.

Key words: ergonym, institution, organization, types of ergonomism, onomastics, ktematonym, trade-specific ergonomisms, non-trade-specific ergonomisms.

Ergonomics (Greek: - work, work and - law) is a science that comprehensively studies a person (a group of people) in relation to the conditions of production activity; researches the interaction and relations of people, technology, production environment for the purpose of improving working tools, conditions and processes. From ancient times, inventing the perfect working tool, studying the condition of the human body during work was connected with the goals of creating the most optimal conditions for performing a task. The first steps towards the creation of the most suitable working tools and the most comfortable working conditions for human activity began at the threshold of the 20th century. The first large-scale practical research in this field was carried out by the American practical engineer and manager, the founder of the school of scientific management, U. F. Taylor (see Taylorism). E. appeared as a scientific and applied science under the influence of the practical needs of production, the increasing role of the human factor in the activities of enterprises, and the development of science and technology. It was formed under the influence of experimental psychology, physiology and labor hygiene; uses data and methodology of medicine, biol., biomechanics, anthropometry, psychophysiology, sociology, mathematics, engineering and technological sciences, principles of labor organization and normalization, is related to general and social psychology, labor economics, economic-mathematical modeling.

After the independence of our country, our life changed dramatically, foreign economic and cultural relations entered the stage of development. As a result, many farms, firms, trade-related shops, and private enterprises began to appear. As each object appears, it must have a name. These innovations, which started in

the 90s of the last century, have now reached their peak. In turn, many new terms entered the science of linguistics. In his research, E. Begmatov lists the following terms that exist in the Uzbek language: anthroponymy, zoonymy, theonymy, toponymy, cosmonymy, phytonymy, chrononymy, polytonymy, ergonymy, phaleronymy, dignitonymy, poreonymy, mythonymy, anemony, stratonym, hemeronym, ideonym. The researcher comments on 15 of these 19 terms and notes that most of them are still waiting for their researchers in Uzbek linguistics [1]. Among them there are ergonyms. It should also be emphasized that these objects, which are formed on the basis of positive changes in our life, should have their proper names. In this matter, the cultural level, taste, wisdom of the people, in general, the development of linguistics and literary studies in the era of globalization, and educational technologies 67 mentality of the nation play a big role. In Western countries, including Russia, ergonomic terms deserve attention in terms of their essence. Usually, ergonyms occupy an intermediate position between trade names and non-trade names. There is no legal law that says it should be placed in any organization. If we look at the main terms and take into account names of a commercial and non-commercial nature, his system is as follows. The term "ctematonym" is a general or cognate term for urbanonyms, trade names, and ergonyms. Urbanonym may or may not be commercial. For this reason, even if they are related to trade nomination, they cannot get a place in this direction in full. Urbanonyms also include oikodonim (the name of a desired building). In full, ergonyms can be grouped as follows: Emporonyms for trade nomination (name of trade organizations)..

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